

A LIGHTWEIGHT FRAMEWORK FOR MELODIC INFORMATION ENCODING AND REAL-TIME REPRODUCTION FOR INTERACTIVE SONIFICATION APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The use of music in interactive sonification applications is a promising alternative to the simple and often aesthetically unappealing sonic textures used in a considerable proportion of designs. Using synthesized music can be advantageous over pre-recorded music, as the system may exert complete control over individual sonic elements to yield sonically diverse and engaging interactions. The real-time generation of interesting, user-tailored music in an auditory display is a complex process but may be significantly streamlined. The proposed demo showcases a twofold system for rapid and lightweight encoding of polyphonic musical information as well as real-time reproduction of this data format in the user's choice of sonic textures. The system was originally designed for use in a gait sonification system in neurorehabilitation, but may be adapted for multiple data types.

1. BACKGROUND

Despite the promising results that interactive sonification has shown in laboratory settings, auditory guidance at large struggles to find its place in commercial applications. Parisehian et. al. [1] suggest the lack of aesthetic considerations and general formalization of the sonification design process as explanations for this limited adoption. The type of sounds generally used may induce fatigue, or not cater to the taste of the user. Effectiveness and efficiency of auditory guidance have been well-investigated, but the notion of user satisfaction has been absent from most research in this area [1]. Indeed, user preferences vary widely and unpredictably, and the need for user-customizable sonification strategies is inevitable.

I focus on key application areas of interactive sonification such as motor (re)learning and neurological rehabilitation [2] [3], where designers desire that a user engages with the technology repeatedly and frequently in situations that demand high endurance and perseverance. While even the most basic sonic textures such as test signals or white noise can be manipulated to provide effective auditory guidance

[1], such designs fail to fully exploit the potential sonic interaction possibilities. Maes et. al. [2] advocate the use of music in movement sonification applications, for its capability to motivate, monitor and modify movement by enhancing self-awareness through extension of the sensory domain. Musical sonification has been applied in multiple applications, such as the D-Jogger [4], and moBeat [5], and multiple studies have shown that feelings of agency through real sonic interaction with music reduce perceived exertion [6] and enhance mood [7].

However, the use of music brings its own set of practical obstacles to the sonification design process. Pre-recorded music (aside from introducing copyright concerns) affords limited interactive signal manipulation without the introduction of unpleasant sonic artifacts. Real-time synthesized music on the other hand allows far more creative interaction possibilities, through spontaneous alterations to musical structure, audio effects and timbre. Moreover, modern computers are more than capable of synthesizing and processing multiple audio tracks while capturing and computing sonification control data. While the design possibilities are no doubt attractive, realizing a system capable of catering to diverse user groups is a multi-faceted challenge. User familiarity has been shown to be a significant factor in the movement-music connection [8].

From a system standpoint, these requirements would necessitate a protocol for flexible encoding of musical information, and a system to decode this information and synthesize user-chosen musical passages in a selection of musical styles, to which target-based sonification metaphors may be applied [1]. It is acknowledged that MIDI is certainly capable of detailed encoding of melodic information. While music-MIDI transcription models exist [9], the process is not trivial and the direct use of existing MIDI files is relatively unreliable in sonification applications. Usable MIDI files for desired music may not always be available, and unpredictable inconsistencies in sound reproduction quality may be introduced by the lack of standardization exhibited by MIDI file creators - for example in terms of octave choices, note velocities and voicing. Furthermore, the rigorous evaluation of sonification strategies would entail a sonic consistency relatively robust to the user's music choice.

The proposed system addresses the aesthetic problem by allowing real-time synthesis of user-chosen music, while opening possibilities for interesting sonification techniques through audio effects and music manipulations that would

be difficult to achieve with pre-recorded music (e.g. D-Jogger). Such an interactive system has the potential to improve adherence in a therapeutic setting, as well as general user retention in other applications. It also streamlines the music structure encoding and decoding processes by standardizing data properties like octaves, polyphony control, voicing and articulation for discrete sonic styles. A robust evaluation procedure inspired by [10] is also planned.

2. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed demo aims to first showcase a lightweight polyphonic representation scheme capable of rapidly encoding simplified versions of short melodic passages as integer codes, complete with real-time previewing and editing. These structures are then decoded and reproduced in real-time by a sequencer with added instrumentation in an array of musical styles. The scheme was designed to assist the testing of a gait rehabilitation application, and correspondingly the time signature is fixed at 4/4 with binary patterns suited to human walking [3]. Regardless, similar schemes can streamline the iterative development of user-flexible interactive systems in various applications.

Both the encoder and decoder are written in JUCE (C++) and audio synthesis is carried out in FAUST. The encoder scheme represents melody passages as a combination of a chord pattern and a monophonic melody. Each passage is a four bar (measure) segment, and scale, pitch, velocity, note octave and chord type information is encoded at a sixteenth-note temporal resolution. Thus, an eight-digit integer code corresponds to two beats, and a passage requires eight such codes. The information is represented in a compressed format, for example velocity only has ten levels (0-9) and pitch is stored as scale degrees (1-9), allowing a compact representation. For example, a velocity code of ‘90009000’ represents a quarter note pattern while one of ‘90909090’ is an eighth note. The encoder application allows a user to create up to five passages, monitor the music in real-time and save the passages in CSV format.

The decoder reads the stored melody and chord structures from the CSV and reproduces the passages in the user’s choice of styles at any tempo. Timekeeping is handled by a master clock that generates a sixteenth note impulse train, and a sequencer tracks pulses to update musical time counters and fetch melodic information from the encoded format in real-time. Musical evolution over time is defined within the sequencer, but may be altered to suit the situation. The decoder also has a library of style-appropriate percussion patterns represented as velocity codes, and the exact chosen percussion pattern is randomized each time. The musical information is mapped to the FAUST synthesis program at every clock interval, where the information is ultimately converted into audio signals and played back.

3. DEMO DESCRIPTION

The rapid real-time encoding process will be showcased, and the sonic possibilities will be auditioned and assessed by participants. As this is part of ongoing work, the sonification system may be in need of further testing but sugges-

tions and ideas will be welcomed, as well as ideas for gestural mapping. Subjective ratings of the synthesized music will also be instrumental in honing the design of the synthesis algorithms.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Parseihian, S. Ystad, M. Aramaki, and R. Kronland-Martinet, “The Process of Sonification Design for Guidance Tasks,” *Wi:Journal of Mobile Media*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-01230638>
- [2] P.-J. Maes, J. Buhmann, and M. Leman, “3mo: A Model for Music-Based Biofeedback,” *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 1, 12 2016.
- [3] N. Schaffert, T. B. Janzen, K. Mattes, and M. H. Thaut, “A Review on the Relationship Between Sound and Movement in Sports and Rehabilitation,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 10, p. 244, 2019.
- [4] B. Moens, C. Muller, L. van Noorden, M. Frank, B. Celie, J. Boone, J. Bourgois, and M. Leman, “Encouraging Spontaneous Synchronisation with D-Jogger, an Adaptive Music Player that Aligns Movement and Music,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 9, 12 2014.
- [5] B. Vlist, C. Bartneck, and S. Mueller, “Mobeat: Using Interactive Music to Guide and Motivate Users During Aerobic Exercising,” *Applied Psychophysiology and Biofeedback*, vol. 36, pp. 135–45, 03 2011.
- [6] T. Fritz, S. Hardikar, M. Demoucron, M. Niessen, M. Demey, O. Giot, Y. Li, J.-D. Haynes, A. Villringer, and M. Leman, “Musical Agency Reduces Perceived Exertion During Strenuous Physical Performance,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 110, 10 2013.
- [7] T. Fritz, J. Halfpaap, S. Grahl, A. Kirkland, and A. Villringer, “Musical Feedback During Exercise Machine Workout Enhances Mood,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 4, p. 921, 12 2013.
- [8] K. S. Park, C. Hass, B. Fawver, H. Lee, and C. Janelle, “Emotional States Influence Forward Gait During Music Listening Based on Familiarity with Music Selections,” *Human Movement Science*, vol. 66, pp. 53–62, 03 2019.
- [9] E. Benetos and S. Dixon, “A Shift-Invariant Latent Variable Model for Automatic Music Transcription,” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 81–94, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41819549>
- [10] G. Parseihian, C. Gondre, M. Aramaki, R. Kronland-Martinet, and S. Ystad, “Exploring the usability of sound strategies for guiding task: toward a generalization of sonification design,” in *Proc. of the 10th International Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research*, Marseille, France, Oct. 2013.